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Additional data on ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Peloponnese

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Abstract: A list of 89 species or morphospecies of ants collected in 2021 and 2023 in Arcadia, southern Argolis, western Corinthia and northern Laconia administrative units is presented. *Temnothorax albipennis* (CURTIS, 1854) and an undescribed species of the genus *Crematogaster* are recorded from Greece for the first time and 9 species or morphospecies are firstly recorded from the Peloponnese. Thus, the list of ant species and morphospecies known from the Peloponnese increased to 153.

Key words: ants, Greece, Peloponnese, Arkadia, Korinthia, Lakonia, faunistics.

INTRODUCTION

This paper is a continuation of a series of papers focused on faunistic investigation of Greek regions. So far, the project has covered Greek islands: Cephalonia (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2014), Corfu (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2021a), Crete (SALATA *et al.* 2020), Dodecanese (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2021), Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018d), Lemnos (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2022), Samos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018b), Samothraki (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2022), Thassos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022a, b, BOROWIEC *et al.* 2022), Zakynthos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018c), and continental provinces: Epirus (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018a), Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017, 2021b), Thrace (BRAČKO *et al.* 2016) and Thessaly (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018b). Numerous new faunistic data were also given in several faunistic and taxonomic papers (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012, 2013, Csösz *et al.* 2018, SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017, 2018, 2019a, 2019b, 2019c, 2022, SALATA *et al.* 2018a, b, 2019, 2021, 2023, SCUPOLA & BOROWIEC 2023, DEMETRIOU *et al.* 2023).

The Peloponnese, one of the geographical and historical regions of Greece, is the southernmost part of the Grecian mainland and is bordered by Sterea Ellas to the north. In the new administrative division of Greece, the Peloponnese is divided into two regions: the Peloponnese and Western Greece. We decided to retain the geographical point of view for this region used by LEGAKIS (2011) because in the past several species were recorded

generally from the peninsula without precise region. The Peloponnese is a peninsula covering an area of some 21,549.6 square kilometres. It has a deeply indented coastline and interior with numerous mountain ranges and the highest point at 2,407 metres (Mount Taygetos).

The ant fauna of the Peloponnese is moderately known, with 142 species or morphospecies recorded (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2021b). Previous studies by the authors based mostly on material collected in northern and southern part of the peninsula (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017, 2021b). In the present paper we provide a list of species collected in southern Argolis, western Corinthia, northern Laconia and, above all, the province of Arcadia, where the data from only a few locations were known until now. In these areas, mountain massifs with a distinct alpine zone (Killini, Menalo and northern Parnon mountain ranges), where we expected to find endemic ant species, were mainly explored.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

All samples were collected by the first author. The main method, applied at all sites, was direct sampling (hand collecting). Ant nests and individual specimens were collected on the ground, in leaf litter, under stones, in dead wood, on tree trunks and twigs. Ants were brushed off to the entomological umbrella on the roadsides and forest. Nests were also searched in rocks cracks and on cracked stones using a chisel. All specimens were preserved in pure 75% and 96% ethanol. Images of ant specimens were taken using a Nikon SMZ 1500 stereomicroscope, Nikon D5200 photo camera and Helicon Focus software. Distribution in Greece refers to BOROWIEC (2014), SALATA and BOROWIEC (2018) and unpublished data from the Database and Collection of Greek Ants (DCGA), preserved at the University of Wrocław. Geographical coordinates are given in the decimal system. Material is deposited in the Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław (in temporary deposit by DBET – Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy, Mymecological Lab, Poland – coll. L. Borowiec).

LIST OF LOCALITIES

Arcadia

- PEL23_161 – Parnon Mts, rd to Kastanitsa, ad. A. Panteleimon, 338 m, 37.31038 / 22.69813, 13 V 2023; roadsides with herbs and shrubs.
- PEL23_162 – Parnon Mts, Kastanitsa, 868 m, 37.25847 / 22.64858, 13 V 2023; water source, on stone walls and masonry.
- PEL23_163 – Parnon Mts, road to Sitena, 772 m, 37.27447 / 22.65289, 13 V 2023; crystalline lime tuff in oak thickets, on stones.
- PEL23_164 – Parnon Mts, ad Sitena, 723 m, 37.28927 / 22.65838, 13 V 2023; heavily sunlit rock wall at roadside, in rock crevices.
- PEL23_165 – Parnon Mts, 1.4 km NE of Sitena, 749 m, 37.30126 / 22.65989, 13 V 2023; Mediterranean shrubs with crystalline lime tuffs.
- PEL23_166 – Parnon Mts, ad Charadros, 664 m, 37.335099 / 22.67399, 13 V 2023; pastures with shrubs and stones.
- PEL23_167 – Parnon Mts, ad Ag. Joannis, 757 m, 37.35846 / 22.62851, 14 V 2023; water source, on stone walls and masonry.
- PEL23_172 – Parnon Mts, 1.8 km W of Dragoumi loc. 1, 930 m, 37.40286 / 22.50482, 15 V 2023; roadsides with shrubs.

- PEL23_173 – Parnon Mts, 1.8 km W of Dragoumi loc. 2, 959 m, 37.39817 / 22.502847, 15 V 2023; dirty road with shrubs on sides.
- PEL23_174 – Parnon Mts, ad Kastri, 983 m, 37.35639 / 22.52906, 15 V 2023; water source, on stone walls and masonry.
- PEL23_175 – Parnon Mts, 1.2 km S of Kastri, 960 m, 37.35122 / 22.52841, 15 V 2023; roadsides with shrubs.
- PEL23_176 – Parnon Mts, ad Elatos loc. 1, 944 m, 37.3477 / 22.54299, 15 V 2023; roadsides with shrubs.
- PEL23_177 – Parnon Mts, ad Elatos loc. 2, 863 m, 37.34889 / 22.54506, 15 V 2023; water source, on stone walls and masonry.
- PEL23_178 – Parnon Mts, Nea Hora, 725 m, 37.36870 / 22.54500, 15 V 2023; from herbs on the rock.
- PEL23_179 – 600 m N of Nea Hora, 638 m, 37.37269 / 22.5488, 15 V 2023; stream valley in plane forest, on stones.
- PEL23_184 – Eleochori, 551 m, 37.46350 / 22.57662, 16 V 2023; heavily sunlit rock wall at roadside.
- PEL23_185 – Mt Mainalo, 2.3 km W of Kardaras, 1308 m, 37.62998 / 22.26654, 17 V 2023; rock wall in fir forest.
- PEL23_186 – Mt Mainalo, road to Mainalo Ski Centre, 1518 m, 37.64241 / 22.26779, 17 V 2023; mountain pasture with rocks.
- PEL23_187 – Mt Mainalo, above Ski Centre loc. 1, 1616 m, 37.65555 / 22.26560, 17 V 2023; rocks in alpine area.
- PEL23_188 – Mt Mainalo, above Ski Centre loc. 2, 1626 m, 37.65948 / 22.25973, 17 V 2023; rocks in alpine area.
- PEL23_189 – Mt Mainalo, road to Vytina loc. 1, 1549 m, 37.66412 / 22.24986, 17 V 2023; rocks in fir forest.
- PEL23_190 – Mt Mainalo, road to Vytina loc. 2, 1468 m, 37.67343 / 22.2331, 17 V 2023; rocks in mountain meadow.
- PEL23_191 – Mt Mainalo, Vytina, 1174 m, 37.67545 / 22.20608, 17 V 2023; rock in fir forest.
- PEL23_192 – Parnon Mts, ad Moni Elonis, 530 m, 37.14598 / 22.76413, 18 V 2023; rock wall at roadside.
- PEL23_193 – Parnon Mts, road to Kosmas, 864 m, 37.13345 / 22.75935, 18 V 2023; on shrubs around mountain meadow.
- PEL23_194 – Parnon Mts, ad Kosmas, 1182 m, 37.08622 / 22.72277, 18 V 2023; rocks in fir forest.
- PEL23_195 – Parnon Mts, 0.9 km W of Kosmas, 1044 m, 37.09480 / 22.7300, 18 V 2023; mixed forest, from shrubs.
- PEL23_196 – Parnon Mts, 2.7 km S of Paleochori, 1100 m, 37.13355 / 22.71194, 18 V 2023; fir and cypress forest with limestone rocks.
- PEL23_197 – Mt Ditiko Mainalo, 1.6 km NW of Chrisivitsi, 1125 m, 37.55723 / 22.19665, 19 V 2023; mountain meadow with rocks in fir forest.
- PEL23_198 – Mt Ditiko Mainalo, 1.9 km NW of Chrisivitsi, 1142 m, 37.56139 / 22.19772, 19 V 2023; fir forest.

- PEL23_199 – Mt Ditiko Mainalo, 1.4 km S of Limbovisi, 1131 m, 37.57132 / 22.18845, 19 V 2023; water source in very shadow fir forest, on stone wall.
- PEL23_200 – Mt Ditiko Mainalo, ad Limbovisi, 1186 m, 37.58202 / 22.19006, 19 V 2023; fir forest with rocks.
- PEL23_201 – Mt Ditiko Mainalo, Chalkovrisi, 1306 m, 37.583737 / 22.17475, 19 V 2023; meadow in fir forest.
- PEL23_202 – Mt Ditiko Mainalo, 4.9 km S of Elati, 1279 m, 37.58806 / 22.17746, 19 V 2023; rocks in fir forest.
- PEL23_203 – Paralia Astros, 0 m, 37.42375 / 22.76574, 20 V 2023; salines at seashore.

Argolis

- PEL23_000 – Kiveri, 1 m, 37.52443 / 22.73181, 12 V 2023, seashore and urban area.
- PEL23_180 – road to Kotsonis, 78 m, 37.491815 / 22.66703, 16 V 2023; dry river bed, from herbs and shrubs.
- PEL23_181 – Kotsonis Estate, 85 m, 37.48927 / 22.66301, 16 V 2023; dry river bed, from herbs and shrubs.
- PEL23_182 – ad Andritsa, 155 m, 37.4748 / 22.62414, 16 V 2023; Mediterranean shrubs.
- PEL23_183 – Ag. Nektarios, 436 m, 37.47426 / 22.59012, 16 V 2023; Mediterranean shrubs and under stones.

Corinthia

- PEL21_024 – Killini Mts., Mt. Ziria loc. 1, 1543 m, 22 VI 2021, 37.94662 / 22.42768, alpine pastures.
- PEL21_025 – Killini Mts., Mt. Ziria loc. 2, 1488 m, 22 VI 2021, 37.98157 / 22.42645, fir and pine forest close to lake.
- PEL21_026 – Killini Mts., Mt. Ziria loc. 3, 1479 m, 22 VI 2021, 37.968 / 22.44395, rest area in fir forest.

Laconia

- PEL23_168 – Parnon Mts, Mt Megali Tourla loc. 1, 1643 m, 37.28538 / 22.60603, 14 V 2023; mountain plateau.
- PEL23_169 – Parnon Mts, Mt Megali Tourla loc. 2, 1655 m, 37.28107 / 22.60529, 14 V 2023; mountain plateau.
- PEL23_170 – Parnon Mts, Mt Megali Tourla loc. 3, 1637 m, 37.28785 / 22.60661, 14 V 2023; fir forest with rocks.
- PEL23_171 – Parnon Mts, Mt Megali Tourla, Kefaloneri, 1129 m, 37.29333 / 22.59179, 14 V 2023; stream valley with fir and plane trees.

LIST OF SPECIES

1. *Aphaenogaster balcanica* (EMERY, 1898)

Localities: 000, 026, 165, 166, 167, 173, 174, 176, 178, 182, 193, 194, 197, 203.

Note: It is a common species recorded from most of the Greek provinces, except Crete, Thessaly and Thrace. In Peloponnese is one of the most common ants in sunny and warm open habitats and luminous forests.

2. *Aphaenogaster epirotes* (EMERY, 1895)

Localities: 163, 165, 166.

Note: *A. epirotes* is a common species, recorded from the Eastern Aegean Islands, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. Prefers shadow and humid habitats. Populations from Peloponnese differs from populations of central and northern Greece in sculpture of head less reticulate with predominate longitudinal rugae.

3. *Aphaenogaster peloponnesiaca* SALATA, KARAMAN, KIRAN & BOROWIEC, 2021

Localities: 162, 167, 174, 179.

Note: It is a recently described endemic Greek species. So far, noted from Argolis, Arcadia, Laconia and Messinia units of Peloponnese, and *Aetolia-Acarmania* and *Beotia* units of Sterea Ellas. The species prefers dark forest habitats.

4. *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 162, 174, 178, 179, 197, 199, 200.

Note: It is one of the commonest species, so far noted from all Greek provinces except Crete. Its nests were observed under stones in shadowy places inside both, deciduous and coniferous forests.

5. *Aphaenogaster* cf. *subterranea*

Localities: 171, 188, 197.

Note: It is an undescribed endemic Greek species belonging to the separate complex within *A. subterranea* species group characterized by completely microsculptured head, pronotum and presense of setose tubercle in anterolateral pronotal corners. This complex is now under detailed study including morphometry, maybe it is a group of cryptic species or only single species variable geographically. Samples of specimens from this complex were noted from Cyclades (Naxos), the Ionian Islands, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. Prefers fir forests but occasionally observed in deciduous forest and olive plantation.

6. *Bothriomyrmex communista* SANTSCHI, 1919

Locality: 186.

Note: It is a common species, noted from most of Greek provinces except Crete and Cyclades. Prefers extremely warm and sunny open habitats.

7. *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 165, 166, 167, 169, 172, 173, 176, 180, 182, 183, 193, 197.

Note: It is a very common species, noted from all Greek provinces and both natural and agricultural habitats.

8. *Camponotus boghossiani* FOREL, 1911

Localities: 024, 025, 026, 162, 167, 196.

Note: It is a southern and eastern species in Greece, known from the Aegean Islands, Crete, Cyclades and the Dodecanese, from mainland Greece known only from Peloponnese. Prefers warm mediterranean habitats, especially shrubs on sunny borders of roads and forests.

9. *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 161, 162, 163, 166, 172, 173, 176, 177, 178, 179, 182, 193, 195.

Note: It is a northern and western species in Greece, known from all mainland provinces, and Aegean and Ionian islands. In Peloponnese it is a very common species most often associated with warm borders of deciduous and mixed forests, mediterranean shrubs, and herbs growing along roadsides.

10. *Camponotus gestroi* EMERY, 1878

Localities: 165, 181, 182, 183, 193.

Note: Populations from northern and central Peloponnese have characters of nominotypical subspecies so far noted from the Aegean and Ionian Islands, and almost all mainland provinces except Epirus. It prefers warm mediterranean habitats, such like shrubs along roadsides, borders of deciduous and coniferous forests and pastures.

11. *Camponotus ionius* EMERY, 1920

Localities: 000, 181.

Note: It is a common species known from all Greek provinces except Crete. Prefers warm and sunny open and semiopen habitats, often noted from tourist resorts and cities in gardens and ruderal sites.

12. *Camponotus kiesenwetteri* (ROGER, 1859)

Localities: 165, 181, 182, 193.

Note: The species was recorded from most of Greek provinces except Epirus. It is strongly associated with pine forests, occasionally noted from mediterranean shrubs along roadsides and river shores.

13. *Camponotus laconicus* EMERY, 1920

Localities: 165, 183, 184.

Note: It is a rare endemic Greek species, known only from Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas provinces. Very thermophilous species, inhabits luminous pine forests, pastures with oak shrubs, roadsides with rocks and frygana, dry valleys of periodic rivers, fryganas with oak shrubs and stream valleys with luminous deciduous forest.

14. *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER, 1792)

Localities: 000, 161, 167, 172, 173, 174, 177, 178, 180, 181, 193.

Note: It is one of the commonest Greek ants known from all provinces. Observed in urban areas on various shrubs and herbs, deciduous and coniferous forests, but it is most common on mediterranean shrubs growing along roadsides.

15. *Camponotus ligniperda* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Locality: 188.

Note: In Greece, this species is known only from mountains of mainland provinces except Thrace, and was also noted from the Ionian Islands. It prefers coniferous forests and rocky alpine pastures.

16. *Camponotus nitidescens* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 162, 186.

Note: It is a rare Greek endemic species noted only from the Ionian Islands, Peloponnese and western Sterea Ellas provinces. Reported from coniferous forests, stream valley with mixed forest and mountain pastures with oak shrubs.

17. *Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 024, 026, 174, 175, 185, 195.

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces. It prefers open habitats like pastures, roadsides, mountain meadows but was occasionally collected also in luminous deciduous and coniferous forests but avoids agricultural habitats.

18. *Camponotus piceus* (LEACH, 1825)

Localities: 024, 026, 172, 173, 175, 176, 197, 203.

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces. Noted mostly from shrubs on mountain pastures and along roadsides, also on shrubs along borders of deciduous, mixed and fir forests.

19. *Camponotus vagus* (SCOPOLI, 1763)

Localities: 025, 162, 170, 177.

Note: It is a common species in Greek mainland, and in islands it is known only from the Aegean and Ionian Islands. *C. vagus* is dendrophilous species associated with old deciduous and coniferous trees especially rotting ones, but it also builds nests in wooden technical devices.

20. *Cardiocondyla mauritanica* FOREL, 1890

Locality: 000, 203.

Note: Invasive species, in Greece noted from the Aegean Islands, Crete, Cyclades, the Dodecanese, the Ionian Islands and Sterea Ellas. New to Peloponnese. It is associated usually with anthropogenic habitats. Collected in seashore with frygana and pine trees, on sandy and gravel river banks with plane trees, in gardens on lawn or ground, on gravel coasts near harbors, on stone walkways around monasteries, regularly observed on lawns insides tourist resorts and cities.

21. *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ, 1833)

Localities: 163, 182.

Note: It is a common species known from all Greek provinces except Cyclades and Crete. It is an extremely thermophilous species, active midday on sandy roads, roadsides with mediterranean shrubs, urban rural areas and pastures.

22. *Colobopsis truncata* (SPINOLA, 1808)

Localities: 162, 172.

Note: It is a common species, recorded from all Greek provinces except Cyclades. Arboricolous species in various types of habitats as deciduous forests along streams, roadsides with shrubs and herbs, old olive trees, pine forests, pastures with fig trees and beaches with deciduous trees.

23. *Crematogaster ionia* FOREL, 1911

Localities: 161, 163, 165, 166, 173, 179, 182, 200.

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces, especially on islands. With great probability this taxon is a complex of cryptic taxa and now is studied based on molecular methods (our unpublished data). *C. ionia* is an arboricolous species associated with lining and dead trees in warm and sunny sites.

24. *Crematogaster* cf. *schmidti* sp. nov.

Locality: 168.

Note: It is an undescribed species from the *Crematogaster schmidti* complex. Its description is in preparation in a separate paper. Nest was located on a rock between two flat limestone slabs in the alpine zone of the mountain plateau of the Megali Tourla massif.

25. *Crematogaster schmidti* (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 000, 162, 172, 173, 174, 175, 176, 177, 178, 180, 181, 192, 193, 195, 196.

Note: The species is known from all Greek Provinces, common in mainland Greece and northern archipelagos, but rare in southern islands. *C. schmidti* is a dendrophilous species, nesting inside dry trunks and branches of various shrubs and trees.

26. *Crematogaster sordidula* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 000, 163, 167, 193.

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces. It prefers warm mediterranean habitats such as pastures, mediterranean shrubs and roadsides. Nests located under stones or directly in ground.

27. *Dolichoderus quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS, 1771)

Localities: 162, 174, 176, 195.

Note: is a moderately common species, known from most Greek provinces except Cyclades. *D. quadripunctatus* is dendrophilous species, prefers shadow habitats, close to streams and rivers.

28. *Formica cunicularia* LATREILLE, 1798

Localities: 162, 168, 172, 174, 175, 193, 195.

Note: It is common in northern mainland provinces and moderately common in southern mainland, on islands noted only from the Aegean Islands and Crete.

29. *Formica fusca* LINNAEUS, 1758

Localities: 024, 169, 171, 194.

Note: *F. fusca* is a mountain species noted from all mainland provinces, on islands reported only from the Ionian Islands and Euboea. Prefers shadow mountain coniferous forests.

30. *Formica sanguinea* LATREILLE, 1798

Localities: 024, 026, 170.

Note: In Greece noted only from mainland provinces except Epirus. It prefers mountain coniferous forests.

31. *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Localities: 162, 187, 200.

Note: Species known from all Greek provinces, but common only in northern and central mainland. In Peloponnese it was observed in rural sites in tourist resorts, mixed and fir forests and mountain pastures.

32. *Lasius bombycina* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI, 2016

Locality: 202.

Note: It is a recently described species but known from all mainland Greek provinces and the Ionian Islands. In Peloponnese it was observed in rural sites in mountain pastures, both coniferous and deciduous forests, olive plantations and tourist resorts.

33. *Lasius brunneus* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 171, 199.

Note: In Greece, it is a rare species although it is known from all mainland provinces, also from the Aegean and Ionian Islands. It prefers shadow and wet mountain forests growing on high altitudes.

34. *Lasius flavus* (FABRICIUS, 1782)

Localities: 024, 026, 162, 186, 198, 201.

Note: Like previous species, in Greece it is rather rare species although it is known from all mainland provinces and from the Aegean and Ionian Islands. Prefers mountain forests, in high altitudes noted also from pastures.

35. *Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN, 1935

Localities: 025, 026, 170, 173, 174, 176, 177, 178, 185, 186, 197, 199, 201, 202.

Note: *L. illyricus* is common in mainland Greece and the Ionian Islands, rare in the Aegean Islands and Crete, and so far not recorded from Cyclades and the Dodecanese. It prefers warm deciduous forests and mediterranean shrubs, but in Peloponnese it was noted also from mountain pastures and luminous fir forests.

36. *Lasius lasioides* (EMERY, 1869)

Localities: 161, 163, 172, 184, 192, 193, 195.

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces. It prefers warm habitats, such as pastures, mediterranean shrubs and luminous deciduous forests.

37. *Lasius turcicus* SANTSCHI, 1921

Localities: 024, 161, 175, 197, 202.

Note: It is an uncommon species, recorded from all Greek provinces except Thessaly. Prefers shadow and wet habitats, mostly close to streams and rivers.

38. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR, 1855)

Localities: 166, 167, 183, 203.

Note: It is a common species, recorded from all Greek provinces. *L. frauenfeldi* is a very thermophilous species, noted from rural sites in urban areas, pine forests, xerothermic meadows and mediterranean shrub.

39. *Lepisiota melas* (EMERY, 1915)

Localities: 000, 164, 192.

Note: It is a common species on Greek island provinces, but are in the mainland, noted only from Macedonia, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thrace. Like previous species prefers very warm and sunny open habitats.

40. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987

Localities: 000, 162, 176.

Note: It is a species common in mainland Greece, rare on islands but known from all provinces except the Ionian Islands. *M. hellenius* is thermophilous, noted from mediterranean shrubs and pastures with limestone rocks.

41. *Messor ibericus* SANTSCHI, 1931

Localities: 024, 168, 173, 174.

Note: It is a common species but still not recorded from Cyclades and Sterea Ellas. It prefers warm open habitats in both lowland and mountain habitats such as xerothermic meadows, mountain pastures, and luminous forests.

42. *Messor structor* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Locality: 167.

Note: It is less common than *M. ibericus*, and is known only from all mainland provinces. It prefers mountain open habitats, in lowlands inhabits less warm and dry habitats as *M. ibericus*.

43. *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, 1910

Locality: 203.

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces. It prefers open habitats of low and mid altitude. In Peloponnese noted from rural site of an urban area, along roadsides with mediterranean shrubs, luminous young mixed forests, and pastures.

44. *Myrmecina graminicola* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Locality: 162.

Note: It is an uncommon species, but recorded from almost all the Greek provinces except the Aegean Islands. Prefers shadow and wet habitats close to streams and river or in moist leaf litter in various types of forests.

45. *Myrmica scabrinodis* NYLANDER, 1846

Localities: 024, 025.

Note: It is an uncommon species, recorded from all mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands. In northern Greece it is known from lowland and mountain habitats, in southern Greece only in mountains. In Peloponnese noted from fir forest, in the border area between fir forest and pasture and from alpine pasture.

46. *Myrmoxenus gordiagini* RUZSKY, 1902

Locality: 186.

Note: It is a social parasite on various *Temnothorax* species, recorded only from Macedonia, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. In Peloponnese observed in nest of an undescribed species of the *Temnothorax tuborum* group temporarily named *Temnothorax* cf. *tuborum*_dark.

47. *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula*

Localities: 161, 162, 163, 165, 166, 167, 179, 181, 183, 196, 198.

Note: Mediterranean populations of the taxon named *Pheidole pallidula* have recently been divided into four species, three of them recorded in Greece (SEIFERT 2016), but this revision is still under discussion owing to the great local variability of this very common Mediterranean ant. SEIFERT (2016) noted from Peloponnese *Pheidole balcanica* SEIFERT, 2016 and *P. koshewnikovi* RUZSKY, 1905.

48. *Plagiolepis perperamus* SALATA, BOROWIEC & RADCHENKO, 2018

Localities: 000, 203.

Note: It is uncommon species but recorded from all Greek provinces. It prefers warm habitats, often collected in anthropogenic habitats in tourist resorts and cities.

49. *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 000, 161, 162, 163, 164, 165, 166, 168, 173, 176, 178, 180, 181, 184, 186, 192, 195, 196, 197, 199, 201, 203.

Note: It is the most common and ubiquitous species of the genus *Plagiolepis*, known from all Greek provinces, from sea coast to mountains up to 2000 m a.s.l. It prefers warm sites, and next to members of the *Pheidole pallidula* complex is often a pioneering species in areas disturbed by human activity.

50. *Plagiolepis taurica* SANTSCHI, 1920

Locality: 024.

Note: According to the recent conception of species of *Plagiolepis taurica* group

by KIRSCHNER *et al.* (2020) in Europe occur three taxa from this complex, two of them: *P. taurica* SANTSCHI, 1920 and *P. pallescens* FOREL, 1889 have been reported from Greece. Re-examination of materials from mainland Greece showed that in Peloponnese occurs only *P. taurica*. It is less common than *P. pygmaea*, found in a wide range of habitats, including mountain steppes in alpine zone.

51. *Ponera coarctata* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Locality: 187.

Note: It is a common species in all mainland provinces but in insular Greece known only from the Ionian Islands.

52. *Prenolepis nitens* (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 172, 173, 176, 178

Note: It is a common species in mainland Greece, in islands noted only from the Aegean and Ionian Islands. It prefers shadow forest habitats, especially oak forests.

53. *Proformica oculatissima* (FOREL, 1886)

Localities: 168, 169, 190.

Note: It is rare Greek endemic species noted only from Peloponnese (Corinthia) and Sterea Ellas (Attica). In our new materials several nests were collected in alpine zone and mountain meadows with sparse vegetation.

54. *Proformica striaticeps* (FOREL, 1911)

Localities: 024, 025.

Note: It is a rare species described from Greek Macedonia (Thessaloniki district) and recorded also from Halkidiki area. Nests observed in mountain meadows and pastures with very sparse vegetation. Population from Killini Mts. has slightly less striate head than population from Halkidiki and its conspecificity with *P. striaticeps* needs confirmed by molecular study because the genus includes several cryptic species with small ranges in mountain areas (LEBAS *et al.* 2023).

55. *Solenopsis juliae* (ARAKELIAN, 1991)

Locality: 162.

Note: The status of most European species of the genus *Solenopsis* requires extensive revision. GALKOWSKI *et al.* (2010) redescribed *Solenopsis fugax* and suggested that four distinct species groups occur in Europe and the Mediterranean region. They also suggested that several taxa proposed by BERNARD (1950) are probably synonyms, but they did not take any formal decisions regarding the nomenclature. In Greece at first glance occur 3-4 morphospecies of *Solenopsis lusitanica* group, status of mainland populations from Greece was clarified recently and they belong to *Solenopsis juliae* (Csősz *et al.* 2023).

56. *Tapinoma* cf. *erraticum* BALC

Localities: 000, 024, 026, 162, 167, 168, 180, 181, 185, 186, 187, 197, 202.

Note: According to B. Seifert's note in WAGNER *et al.* (2018), populations of *Tapinoma erraticum* complex in south-eastern Europe consist of two similar species easily separated by the morphology of male genitalia (see BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022b). They suggested that the true *T. erraticum* is common only in northern parts of the Balkan Peninsula. In Greece, only this still undescribed taxon was found until now and is known from all Greek provinces.

57. *Temnothorax albipennis* (CURTIS, 1854)

Localities: 024, 025, 026, 169, 170, 194.

Note: Due to taxonomic uncertainties regarding the *Temnothorax unifasciatus* complex in the Balkans, this species has not yet been confirmed for Greece. Our present study confirmed its occurrence in the Peloponnese, representing the first records for Greece. Except Peloponnese we have examined specimens of this species previously collected in the mountain areas of Epirus and western Thessaly. It is associated with limestone rocks and all nests were observed in rock crevices.

58. *Temnothorax angulinodis* CSÓSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ, 2015

Locality: 025.

Note: Recently described species, probably endemic to Peloponnese. Hitherto known only from Mainalo Massif in Arcadia, and our specimens were collected in Killini mountains of western Corinthia. Associated with limestone rocks inside fir forests, nests in rock crevices.

59. *Temnothorax arkasi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2022

Locality: 169.

Note: Recently described species, endemic to Greece. Known only from northern part of Parnon Mts. at the border area of Arcadia and Laconia regional units. Associated with limestone rocks in alpine zone, nests in rock crevices.

60. *Temnothorax brackoi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019

Localities: 161, 162, 172, 173, 175, 176, 178, 193, 195.

Note: Recently described species, endemic to Balkans. In Greece recorded from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. Arboricolous species, associated with mediterranean shrubs and small deciduous trees. Nests inside dry stems of various shrubs and trees.

61. *Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL, 1892)

Localities: 161, 163, 172, 177, 178, 193.

Note: It is a moderately common species, known from most of Greek provinces except Crete and Cyclades. It prefers shadow habitats, such as oak forests, especially with stones and rocks, stream valleys in deciduous forests, limestone rocks inside mediterranean shrubs, sometimes in pine forests. Nests were located inside dry branches of trees and shrubs, in rock crevices or under moss on stones.

62. *Temnothorax crasecundus* SEIFERT & CSÓSZ, 2015

Localities: 025, 162, 170, 171, 172, 174, 175, 177, 186, 187, 188, 189, 191, 194, 195, 199, 200, 201.

Note: It is a recently described eastern species, probably vicariant to *Temnothorax crassispinus* (KARAVAIIEV, 1926). From Greece it was recorded only from mainland provinces except Epirus, especially in eastern part of the country. It prefers mountain forests of all types. Workers were observed on stones and dry branches of trees in leaf litter. Nests were located inside dry branches of trees and shrubs, in rock crevices or under moss on stones.

63. *Temnothorax dessyi* (MENOZZI, 1936)

Locality: 193.

Note: It is a rare species endemic to Greece. Recorded from the Dodecanese, Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas. Prefers oak forests, nests were located in rock crevices or under moss on limestone rocks.

64. *Temnothorax* cf. *exilis*

Localities: 161, 164, 184.

Note: The *Temnothorax exilis* complex from Greece needs extensive revision. There are at least 7 morphospecies of unclear taxonomic status collected in this country. Specimens from Peloponnese belong to the morphospecies with mostly shiny surface of head and pronotum, and bicolored body. Such colored morphospecies was usually identified as *Temnothorax leviceps* EMERY, 1898 described from Italy but, due to great variability of *Temnothorax exilis* EMERY, 1869, status of this taxon is unclear. This morphospecies is common in Greece, recorded from all regions. It is a thermophilous species, and prefers sunny rocky habitats.

65. *Temnothorax graecus* (FOREL, 1911)

Localities: 161, 180, 181, 182.

Note: Peloponnese is terra typica for this species, but it occurs in whole southern Balkans. In Greece recorded from Cyclades, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas. It prefers warm habitats with limestone rocks, but was noted also from urban parks, pine forests, mixed forest, limestone quarries, and roadsides with mediterranean shrubs and limestone stones.

66. *Temnothorax helenae* CSÖSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ, 2015

Localities: 026, 172, 174, 175, 176, 185, 197.

Note: It is a recently described species, common and widespread in southern Balkans and northern Turkey. It prefers forest habitats, especially coniferous forests but was observed also in deciduous and mixed forests and pastures with oak trees and stones. Nests were located in cracked rocks and stones or under moss.

67. *Temnothorax* cf. *kemali*

Localities: 161, 180, 181, 182, 193.

Note: It is an undescribed species from *T. kemali* species group. Revision of this group is under preparation. In Greece it was collected in the Ionian Islands, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. Arboreal species, nests were observed in dry stems of shrubs and on stones under moss.

68. *Temnothorax laconicus* Csősz *et al.*, 2013

Localities: 162, 163, 171, 174, 176, 177, 178, 179, 187.

Note: It is a recently described species, endemic to Greece. Common in Peloponnese but noted also from the Ionian Islands and western Sterea Ellas. It prefers shadow places inside forests, both deciduous and coniferous. Nests were located in cracked rocks and stones, under moss or inside dry branches of trees.

69. *Temnothorax messiniaensis* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019

Locality: 195.

Note: It is a recently described species, endemic to Greece, and common in the Ionian Islands and Peloponnese. It prefers warm habitats as roadsides with mediterranean shrubs and sunny forest edges. Nests were located inside dry stems of shrubs and large herbs.

70. *Temnothorax morea* CSÖSZ, SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2018

Localities: 024, 026, 187.

Note: It is a recently described species related to *Temnothorax interruptus* (SCHENCK, 1952). It was recorded from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Peloponnese, and Sterea Ellas. It was noted from luminous forests, stream valleys, especially with limestone stones and rocks, mediterranean shrubs and olive plantation. Nests were located in cracked stones or under moss on stones.

71. *Temnothorax* cf. *nigriceps*_long spined

Localities: 186, 187.

Note: Our study of various Greek samples of the *Temnothorax nigriceps* complex showed that there are at least three morphospecies and probably none of them is conspecific with true *T. nigriceps* (MAYR, 1855). This problem will be clarified in a forthcoming revision of this group of species. All morphospecies of this group were noted from alpine parts of all Greek mainland mountains and the highest parts of the Ionian Islands. Nests were in cracked rocks and stones.

72. *Temnothorax* cf. *nigriceps*_reticulate

Localities: 024, 166, 169, 175, 195.

Note: See note under species 71.

73. *Temnothorax* cf. *nigriceps*_short spined

Localities: 024, 169.

Note: See note under species 71.

74. *Temnothorax parnonensis* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2022

Localities: 165, 168, 169, 170, 187.

Note: It is a recently described species, endemic to Greece. All examined specimens were collected in three mountain ranges of Peloponnese: Mainalo, Parnon and Taygetos. Nests were observed in areas overgrown by mediterranean oak forest, young and sparse fir forest and in alpine pastures above the upper border of the forest zone. Nests in rock crevices.

75. *Temnothorax parvulus* (SCHENCK, 1852)

Locality: 194.

Note: It is a rare species in Greece recorded from all mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands. Examined population from Peloponnese belongs to the dark form associated with fir forests.

76. *Temnothorax recondens* (NYLANDER, 1856)

Localities: 178, 196.

Note: It is a common species known from all Greek provinces. Reported from various habitats but usually it prefers shadow stream valleys and rocks located inside various types of forests. Nests in rock crevices or under moss on stones.

77. *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ, 1881)

Localities: 167, 168, 185, 195, 197.

Note: It is an uncommon species although recorded from all Greek provinces except the Ionian Islands. Associated with limestone rocks and stones in open and sunny localities from sea level to alpine pastures, occasionally also inside luminous forests and shrubs. Nests in rock crevices.

78. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_dark

Localities: 168, 169, 186, 188.

Note: In Peloponnese three morphospecies of *Temnothorax tuberum* complex were collected. All probably represent undescribed taxa. They occur in mountain habitats, especially in alpine pastures with limestone rocks but nests were also observed in rock walls along roadsides and on rocks in mountain meadows. The species status of these three taxa will be clarified after a comprehensive revision of the entire *T. tuberum* complex from all the mountains of Greece.

79. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_long spined

Localities: 026, 190.

Note: see note under species no. 78.

80. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_pale

Localities: 176, 185, 190, 197, 200, 201, 202.

Note: see note under species no. 78.

81. *Temnothorax turcicus* (SANTSCHI, 1934)

Localities: 162, 172, 173, 175, 199, 201.

Note: It was recorded from the Aegean Islands, the Dodecanese, Macedonia, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. Arborescent species, prefers warm habitats such as sunny edges of forests, mediterranean shrubs or luminous oak and pine forests. Nests were found in dead wood inside dry tree branches or occasionally under moss on stones.

82. *Temnothorax* cf. *unifasciatus*

Localities: 168, 169, 185, 186, 188, 190, 202.

Note: Status of Peloponnese populations of *Temnothorax unifasciatus* complex is unclear. They differ from typical *T. unifasciatus* from Central Europe in antennal club only slightly infuscate or in some nests only indistinctly darker than basal segments of funiculus and in dark posterior band on first gastral tergite often narrowed in the middle or almost interrupted. At first glance many specimens look similar to typically colored specimens of *T. turcicus* but differ in petiole habitat preference and nesting in rock crevices.

83. *Tetramorium caespitum* (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Localities: 024, 176.

Note: A recent revision of the *Tetramorium caespitum* complex (WAGNER *et al.* 2017) showed that the group contains several cryptic species, thus all old Greek records of *Tetramorium caespitum* need confirmation. SALATA & BOROWIEC (2019c) confirmed its occurrence in Epirus, Macedonia, Peloponnese and Thessaly, and later also noted from Sterea Ellas. Reported from mountain pastures, roadsides with shrubs and meadows in fir forests, nests under stones.

84. *Tetramorium hungaricum* RÖSZLER, 1935

Locality: 197.

Note: It is an uncommon species but noted from all mainland provinces except Sterea Ellas. In Peloponnese rare, known from only single site in Kalamata city of Messinia regional unit. In Arcadia nests were located under stone in mountain meadow with rocks in fir forest, in Messinia on dry hill placed in the centre of Kalamata city.

85. *Tetramorium immigrans* SANTSCHI, 1927

Localities: 000, 203.

Note: It is a tramp species of subcosmopolitan distribution. In Greece, it was noted from most provinces except Cyclades and Epirus. It is known almost exclusively from anthropogenic habitats, urban grasses, parks, and tourist resorts. Only in one site from Crete, it was collected from semi-natural habitat in a distance from regions under strong anthropogenic pressure.

86. *Tetramorium impurum* (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Locality: 169.

Note: In Greece it is a mountain species, noted from Epirus, Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Peloponnese Sterea Ellas and Thrace.

87. *Tetramorium indocile* SANTSCHI, 1927

Locality: 170

Note: It prefers mountain and alpine pastures, nests in ground under stones.

88. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017

Localities: 167, 168, 171, 173, 183, 185, 187.

Note: It is a recently described species but common species, known from all Greek provinces. It is thermophilous, and prefers open habitats such as pastures and roadsides but was noted also from luminous forests and olive plantations. Nests were found in the ground under stones.

89. *Tetramorium moravicum* KRATOCHVIL, 1941

Localities: 174, 202.

Note: It is a common species known from all mainland provinces but absent in island provinces. It occurs in various habitats from sea level to alpine zone in mountains, in open to forest areas but in forests prefers roadsides and clearings. Nests were found in the ground under stones.

UPDATED LIST OF ANTS RECORDED FROM PELOPONNESE

(species new to Greece marked with **, species new to Peloponnese marked with *)

1. *Acropyga paleartica* MENOZZI
2. *Aphaenogaster balcanica* (EMERY)
3. *Aphaenogaster epirotes* (EMERY)
4. *Aphaenogaster finzii* MÜLLER
5. *Aphaenogaster muelleriana* WOLF
6. *Aphaenogaster peloponnesiaca* Salata, KARAMAN, KIRAN & BOROWIEC
7. *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE)
8. *Aphaenogaster* cf. *subterranea* sp. 1
9. *Bothriomyrmex communista* SANTSCHI
10. *Bothriomyrmex corsicus* SANTSCHI
11. *Camponotus* (*Camponotus*) *ligniperda* (LATREILLE)
12. *Camponotus* (*Camponotus*) *vagus* (SCOPOLI)
13. *Camponotus* (*Myrmentoma*) *atricolor* (NYLANDER)
14. *Camponotus* (*Myrmentoma*) *boghossiani* FOREL
15. *Camponotus* (*Myrmentoma*) *dalmaticus* (NYLANDER)
16. *Camponotus* (*Myrmentoma*) *fallax* (NYLANDER)
17. *Camponotus* (*Myrmentoma*) *gestroi* EMERY
18. *Camponotus* (*Myrmentoma*) *kiesenwetteri* (ROGER)
19. *Camponotus* (*Myrmentoma*) *lateralis* (OLIVIER)
20. *Camponotus* (*Myrmentoma*) *nitidescens* FOREL
21. *Camponotus* (*Myrmentoma*) *piceus* (LEACH)

22. *Camponotus (Tanaemyrmex) aethiops* (LATREILLE)
23. *Camponotus (Tanaemyrmex) ionius* EMERY
24. *Camponotus (Tanaemyrmex) laconicus* EMERY
25. *Camponotus (Tanaemyrmex) oertzeni* FOREL
26. *Camponotus (Tanaemyrmex) samius* FOREL
27. *Cardiocondyla dalmatica* SOUDEK
28. *Cardiocondyla mauritanica* FOREL*
29. *Cardiocondyla stambuloffii* FOREL
30. *Carebara oertzeni* FOREL
31. *Cataglyphis hellenica* (FOREL)
32. *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ)
33. *Chalepoxenus muellerianus* (FINZI)
34. *Colobopsis truncata* (SPINOLA)
35. *Crematogaster ionia* FOREL
36. *Crematogaster lorteti* FOREL
37. *Crematogaster schmidti* (MAYR)
38. *Crematogaster sordidula* (NYLANDER)
39. *Crematogaster* cf. *schmidti* sp. nov.**
40. *Cryptopone ochracea* (MAYR)
41. *Dolichoderus quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS)
42. *Formica (Raptiformica) sanguinea* LATREILLE
43. *Formica (Serviformica) clara* FOREL
44. *Formica (Serviformica) cunicularia* LATREILLE
45. *Formica (Serviformica) fusca* LINNAEUS
46. *Formica (Serviformica) gagates* LATREILLE
47. *Formica (Serviformica) rufibarbis* FABRICIUS
48. *Hypoponera eduardi* (FOREL)
49. *Lasius (Austrolasius) carniolicus* MAYR
50. *Lasius (Austrolasius) reginae* FABER
51. *Lasius (Cautolasius) flavus* (FABRICIUS)
52. *Lasius (Cautolasius) myrmidon* MEI
53. *Lasius (Chthonolasius) bicornis* (FÖRSTER)
54. *Lasius (Chthonolasius) distinguendus* (EMERY)
55. *Lasius (Chthonolasius) jensi* SEIFERT
56. *Lasius (Chthonolasius) mixtus* (NYLANDER)
57. *Lasius (Chthonolasius) viehmeyeri* EMERY
58. *Lasius (Lasius) alienus* (FÖRSTER)
59. *Lasius (Lasius) bombycina* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI
60. *Lasius (Lasius) brunneus* (LATREILLE)
61. *Lasius (Lasius) emarginatus* (OLIVIER)

62. *Lasius (Lasius) illyricus* ZIMMERMANN
63. *Lasius (Lasius) lasioides* (EMERY)
64. *Lasius (Lasius) neglectus* VAN LOON, BOOMSMA & ANDRASALVY
65. *Lasius (Lasius) turcicus* SANTSCHI
66. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR)
67. *Lepisiota melas* (EMERY)
68. *Lepisiota nigra* (DALLA TORRE)
69. *Linepithema humile* (MAYR)
70. *Liometopum microcephalum* (PANZER)
71. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD
72. *Messor ibericus* SANTSCHI
73. *Messor structor* (LATREILLE)
74. *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE
75. *Monomorium monomorium* BOLTON
76. *Myrmecina graminicola* (LATREILLE)
77. *Myrmica hellenica* FINZI
78. *Myrmica hirsuta* ELMES
79. *Myrmica pelops* SEIFERT
80. *Myrmica scabrinodis* NYLANDER
81. *Myrmoxenus adlerzi* (DOUWES, JESSEN & BUSCHINGER)
82. *Myrmoxenus gordiagini* RUZSKY*
83. *Myrmoxenus stumperi* (KUTTER)
84. *Nylanderia jaegerskioeldi* (MAYR)
85. *Pheidole balcanica* SEIFERT
86. *Pheidole indica* MAYR
87. *Pheidole koshewnikovi* RUZSKY
88. *Pheidole pallidula* (NYLANDER)
89. *Plagiolepis perperamus* SALATA, BOROWIEC & RADCHENKO
90. *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE)
91. *Plagiolepis taurica* SANTSCHI
92. *Ponera coarctata* (LATREILLE)
93. *Ponera testacea* EMERY
94. *Prenolepis nitens* (MAYR)
95. *Proceratium algericum* FOREL
96. *Proceratium melinum* (ROGER)
97. *Proformica chelmosensis* LEBAS & GALKOWSKI
98. *Proformica oculatissima* (FOREL)*
99. *Proformica striaticeps* (FOREL)
100. *Solenopsis juliae* (ARAKELIAN)
101. *Solenopsis* cf. *lusitanica* sp. 2

102. *Stenamamma debile* (FÖRSTER)
103. *Stigmatomma denticulatum* ROGER
104. *Stigmatomma impressifrons* EMERY
105. *Strongylognathus huberi dalmaticus* BARONI URBANI
106. *Strongylognathus silvestrii* MENOZZI
107. *Tapinoma* cf. *erraticum*_BALC
108. *Tapinoma simrothi* KRAUSSE
109. *Temnothorax albipennis* (CURTIS)**
110. *Temnothorax angulinodis* CSÖSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ
111. *Temnothorax arkasi* SALATA & BOROWIEC
112. *Temnothorax brackoi* SALATA & BOROWIEC
113. *Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL)
114. *Temnothorax crasecundus* SEIFERT & CSÖSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ
115. *Temnothorax crassispinus* (KARAVAEV)
116. *Temnothorax dessyi* (MENOZZI)
117. *Temnothorax* cf. *exilis* (EMERY)
118. *Temnothorax flavicornis* (EMERY)
119. *Temnothorax graecus* (FOREL)
120. *Temnothorax helenae* CSÖSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ
121. *Temnothorax* cf. *kemali**
122. *Temnothorax laconicus* CSÖSZ, SEIFERT, MÜLLER, TRINDL, SCHULZ & HEINZE
123. *Temnothorax* cf. *melanocephalus*
124. *Temnothorax messiniaensis* SALATA & BOROWIEC
125. *Temnothorax morea* CSÖSZ, SALATA & BOROWIEC
126. *Temnothorax* cf. *nigriceps*_long spined
127. *Temnothorax* cf. *nigriceps*_reticulate
128. *Temnothorax* cf. *nigriceps*_short spined*
129. *Temnothorax parnonensis* SALATA & BOROWIEC
130. *Temnothorax parvulus* (SCHENCK)
131. *Temnothorax recedens* (NYLANDER)
132. *Temnothorax rogeri* EMERY
133. *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ)
134. *Temnothorax strymonensis* CSÖSZ, SALATA & BOROWIEC
135. *Temnothorax subtilis* CSÖSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ
136. *Temnothorax tauricus* (RUZSKY)
137. *Temnothorax tergestinus* (FINZI)
138. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_dark*
139. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_long spined
140. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_pale*
141. *Temnothorax turcicus* (SANTSCHI)

142. *Temnothorax* cf. *unifasciatus* (LATREILLE)
143. *Tetramorium caespitum* (LINNAEUS)
144. *Tetramorium chefteki* FOREL
145. *Tetramorium diomedeuem* EMERY
146. *Tetramorium hippocratis* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD
147. *Tetramorium hungaricum* RÖSZLER*
148. *Tetramorium immigrans* SANTSCHI
149. *Tetramorium impurum* (FÖRSTER)
150. *Tetramorium indocile* SANTSCHI*
151. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC
152. *Tetramorium moravicum* KRATOCHVÍL
153. *Tetramorium* cf. *punicum* sp. 1

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